

SeaSciPub Index : Interoperability of Scientific Journal Databases for Scientific Community Among Southeast Asian Countries

Ekawati Marlina

Center for Scientific Documentation and Information Indonesian Institute of Sciences,
Gatot Subroto 10 Jakarta Indonesia, ekawati.marlina@lipi.go.id

Budi Nugroho

Center for Scientific Documentation and Information Indonesian Institute of Sciences,
Gatot Subroto 10 Jakarta Indonesia, budinugroho78@gmail.com

Al Hafiz Akbar Maulana Siagian

Center for Scientific Documentation and Information Indonesian Institute of Sciences,
Gatot Subroto 10 Jakarta Indonesia, alha002@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Scientific journals often become the main reference for the stakeholders, because the information in scientific journals is considered accurate and accountable. Currently, Center for Scientific Documentation and Information - Indonesian Institute of Sciences (PDII LIPI) has been providing services, such as access to the database of Indonesian scientific journals. This service can be accessed online and the number of visitors accessing each year is increasing. Up to October 2014 the site has been accessed by more than 300 thousand users. Due to the large number of visitors who access the site, access to scientific journals in Southeast Asia is provided. Southeast Asian region was chosen because it is located adjacent to the geography of Indonesia and has a condition similar to Indonesia. Moreover, the natural resources are almost the same and the majority regions have a sub-tropical weather. The development of a scientific journal publishing in Indonesia has publishers switched to electronic publishing where most publishers using the platform of the Open Journal System (OJS). By conducting an analysis, it is found out that the publishers in several Southeast Asian countries also use it. One of the advantages of OJS is the facility that allows the interoperability of data harvesting by the portal that does harvester. A web-based indexing system was created to provide the service. Open archives initiatives protocol for metadata harvesting (OAI PMH) was chosen to collect the metadata record because it is open source and easily used. Metadata records were gathered by searching oai url address. This study leads to the achievement of the target product in the form of framework/platform of an open source based software, namely SeaScipub Index (Southeast Asian Countries Scientific Publication Index). By sharing the data, it is expected to improve accessibility, visibility, dissemination and promotion of scientific journals.

Keywords: Interoperability, Indexing system, Scientific journal, Open journal system

1. INTRODUCTION

Scientific journal is a medium to convey the development of science. Prior to publication, a journal has been through the peer review process so that it is guaranteed that the published works can be trusted. This is what made scientific journals serve as the primary reference. In addition, scientists also use them as the main tool for disseminating the results of research. Scientists write research results in the form of scientific journal in order to disseminate research results and to declare that he is the first person to do the research. Dissemination will go well if it is supported by an easy access. The benefit from the easy access, are research acceleration, education enrichment, knowledge sharing, literature usefulness, and laying the foundation for uniting humanity in a common intellectual conversation and quest for knowledge (Swan, 2012).

In overcoming the barriers to access Indonesian scientific journals, in 2009 PDII LIPI developed Indonesian Scientific Journal Database (ISJD). From January to October 2014, this service had been accessed by more than 300 thousand users. At the beginning of the management, it was found that most of the journals were published in printed form. This is one of the obstacles in the management because it must be input manually into the system. To facilitate integration into the database, since 2011 PDII LIPI has initiated to promote electronic journal publishing by using OJS-PKP and has translated the system into the Indonesian version.

Over the last three years, Indonesian publisher who are already using OJS and registered on the site of PKP is steadily increasing. Other Southeast Asian countries, there are also publishers who use this system, although it is not as many as in Indonesia. Therefore, a system for indexing journals published in Southeast Asian countries needs to be built. By using this tool, the visibility, accessibility and dissemination will increase. In Southeast Asia, there has been a repository of digital journals (www.digitaljournal.org), but it is limited only in the health field. The system will index all journals published in scientific journals in Southeast Asian countries which use OJS-PKP. This tool is used as a centralized service scientific papers published in scientific journals for scientific community among Southeast Asian countries and as a tool to share information on research progress in Southeast Asia.

2. STATE OF THE ART OVERVIEW

2.1 Open Journal System

Open Journal Systems (OJS) is a journal management and publishing system that has been developed by the Public Knowledge Project through its federally funded efforts to expand and improve access to research. OJS assists with every stage of the refereed publishing process, from submissions through to online publication and indexing. OJS is open source software made freely available to journals worldwide for the purpose of making open access publishing a viable option for more journals, as open access can increase a journal's readership as well as its contribution to the public good on a global scale.

OJS assists with every stage of the refereed publishing process, from submissions through to online publication and indexing. Through its management systems, its finely grained indexing of research, and the context it provides for research, OJS seeks to improve both the scholarly and public quality of refereed research (<https://pkp.sfu.ca/ojs/>).

OJS is used by many journals around the world. In March 2009, (Edgar & Willinsky) conducted their first survey of journal that deploy OJS, and that paper reports on the results of that survey to which 998 editors or staff member responded. Their study reports on the

OJS experiment, involving the introduction of open source software systems into a site of considerable transformation, namely scholarly communication in the twenty first century. OJS is but one of a number of open source journal management systems. It is being used by approximately 5,000 journals, has had 19 upgrade releases since it was first made available in 2002, and is now available in 20 languages. They also reported that roughly half of OJS users from a developing world.

Based on data reported by PKP, OJS users around the world every year has increased, as shown in Figure 1.

Source : <https://pkp.sfu.ca/ojs/ojs-usage/ojs-stats/>

Figure 1. Journals using Open Journal Systems

2.2 Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH)

The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (AOI-PMH) provides an application-independent interoperability framework based on metadata harvesting (Lagoze & Sompel, The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting). There are two classes of participants in the OAI-PMH framework:

- Data providers : maintains one or more repositories (web servers) that support the OAI-PMH as a mean of exposing metadata, respond to OAI-PMH queries over HTTP, and deliver metadata in XML format; and
- Service providers: issues OAI-PMH request over HTTP to data providers and uses the metadata as a basis for building value-added services.

Source: http://www.uts.utoronto.ca/~chan/oaindia/presentations/OAI_PMH.pdf

Figure 2. Basic Functioning of OAI-PMH

3. METHOD

The method used in the study is to collect data of scientific papers published in scientific journals among Southeast Asian countries, to define protocols of data exchange among databases of scientific papers published in scientific journals among Southeast Asian countries, to develop a web based indexing tools using open source software and to implement the web based indexing tools.

Subject in this study is scientific journals in Southeast Asian countries, which are published using OJS application.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the research will have value if they can be used by stakeholders. Therefore, the results should be disseminated. The easy access is a key element of this dissemination. To support ease of access, the current publishers of journals in Indonesia use electronic publishing systems. All processes, ranging from delivery, receipt, review until the publication process, are conducted online.

Based on the survey until August 2008, active journals listed in PDII-LIPI totaled 2,300 publishers. The amount was increased in August 2012 into 5,703 (Lukman, Marlina, Sari, Akbar, & Riyanto, 2012). From the total number of the active journals, the ones that reported using OJS were 833 publishers (Table. 1).

Based on the data from PKP, OJS users in Southeast Asian countries for the last three years have been increasing, especially for Indonesian. A significant increase was seen in 2011 and 2012. The number of OJS users in Southeast Asia is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. OJS users in Southeast Asia

Country	Total/year		
	2011	2012	2013
Indonesia	558	833	861
Philippines	18	21	38
Malaysia	23	26	25
Thailand	104	105	107
Myanmar	1	1	1
Laos	0	0	0
Brunei	0	0	0
Cambodia	0	0	0
Vietname	32	33	28
Singapore	0	0	0

Source : <https://pkp.sfu.ca/ojs/ojs-usage/ojs-map/>

OJS is widely used because OJS is easy to install and has a comprehensive functions to support the goal of modeling and implementing the operations of a scholarly publication, from author-initiated submission, through peer review, to editing, production, public publication and final archiving (Cyzyk & Choudhury, 2008). Moreover, OJS is equipped with an index of the journal. The indexing in OJS adheres to the Open Archives Initiative Harvesting Protocol (OAI-PMH), which is based in turn, one the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative that utilizes 15 elements. OAI-PMH is a low-barrier mechanism for repository interoperability (Lagoze & Sompel, The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting).

During this time, PDII LIPI only provides information about the scientific journals that exist in Indonesia. With the existence of the database, research results can be easily accessed, it can be seen the duplication of research activities and can be used as a means to detect plagiarism. With the index of journals in a single database, it allows for the use of resources together. According to (Rodliyah, 2012), the benefits of resource sharing are to save money and maximize the utilization of sources of information. By looking at the existing benefits, it will be created a system for indexing journals published in Southeast Asian countries. Southeast Asian region was chosen, because it is located adjacent to the geography of Indonesia and has a condition similar to Indonesia. Moreover, the natural resources are almost the same and the majority regions have a sub-tropical weather. With the same conditions, the possibility of the studies carried out is similar or identical. With the SeaSciPub Index, researchers can easily determine other researchers in Southeast Asia that has the same area of expertise, making it easier for them to work together.

The subject in this study is scientific journals in Southeast Asian countries, which were published by using OJS application. This is to facilitate the interoperability process, a system that allows different systems to communicate with each other. The model of SeaSciPub Index is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. SeaSciPub Index Model

The model of SeaSciPub Index is built based on the OAI-PMH basic functions (Figure 2.). Metadata sharing occurs between the data providers and service providers. OJS as a data provider expose metadata to the harvester and harvester act as a service provider, collecting metadata from OJS. Harvester applications are built using the Open Harvester Systems (OHS), which is a free metadata indexing system developed by the Public Knowledge Project. This system has the ability to harvest OAI metadata in a variety of schemes (including unqualified DC, PKP (Open Journal Systems / Open Conference Systems) Dublin Core extensions, MODS, and MARCXML) and has a flexible search interface that allows simple searching and advanced searching using cross-walked fields from all harvested archives.

OAI url address data were collected by searching through the web search engines. The search results appear in the Table 2, showing that Singapore has 4 journals, Vietnam 2 journals, Malaysia 7 journals, Thailand 5 journals and Indonesia 120 journals. The journals from Philippines and Myanmar were not found. In collecting the data, there was an obstacle, i.e. it

is difficult to get a complete list of users because of OJS is an open source software. PKP has investigated a variety of ways to collect the data of the users, but there is still missing journals. For example, in Singapore based on the existing data in the PKP, no journals uses OJS, but after a search four journals using OJS were found. The list of OAI url addresses and name of the journals is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. OAI url address

Country	Number	Journal Titles	OAI url
Singapore	1	TIJ's Research Journal of Commerce & Behavioural Science - RJCBS	https://www.theinternationaljournal.org/ojs/index.php?journal=rjcbbs
	2	TIJ's Research Journal of Economics & Business Studies - RJEBS	https://www.theinternationaljournal.org/ojs/index.php?journal=rjebbs
	3	TIJ's Research Journal of Science & IT Management - RJSITM	https://www.theinternationaljournal.org/ojs/index.php?journal=rjitsm
	4	TIJ's Research Journal of Social Science & Management - RJSSM	https://www.theinternationaljournal.org/ojs/index.php?journal=tij
Vietname	1	The Journal of Biomedical Research and Therapy BMRAT	http://www.bmrat.org/index.php/bmrat/oai
	2	Journal of Vietnamese Environment	https://oa.slub-dresden.de/ejournals/index.php/ejournals/oai
Malaysia	1	Journals of Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia	http://penerbit.uthm.edu.my/ojs/index.php/ojs/oai
	2	International Journal of Integrated Engineering	http://penerbit.uthm.edu.my/ojs/index.php/ijie/oai
	3	Journal of Science and Technology	http://penerbit.uthm.edu.my/ojs/index.php/JST/oai
	4	Journal of Technical Education and Training	http://penerbit.uthm.edu.my/ojs/index.php/JTET/oai
	5	Journal of Techno-Social	http://penerbit.uthm.edu.my/ojs/index.php/JTS/oai
	6	International Journal of Sustainable Construction Engineering and Technology	http://penerbit.uthm.edu.my/ojs/index.php/IJSCET/oai
	7	Journal of Technology Management and Business	http://penerbit.uthm.edu.my/ojs/index.php/jtmb/oai
Thailand	1	Health Science Journals in Thailand	http://thailand.digitaljournals.org/index.php/digitaljournals/oai
	2	Journal of Health Science วารสารวิชาการสาธารณสุข	http://thailand.digitaljournals.org/index.php/JHS/oai
	3	Buddhachinaraj Medical Journal	http://thailand.digitaljournals.org/index.php/BMJ/oai
	4	Journal of Medicine and Health Sciences	http://thailand.digitaljournals.org/index.php/JMHS/oai
	5	Journal of Srithanya hospital	http://thailand.digitaljournals.org/index.php/JSH/oai
Indonesia	1	Indonesian Journal of Curriculum and Educational Technology Studies	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/jktp/oai
	2	Developmental and Clinical Psychology	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/dcp/oai
	3	Joyful Learning Journal	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/jlj/oai
	4	BELIA: Early Childhood Education Papers	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/belia/oai
	5	Educational Psychology Journal	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/epj/oai
	6	Journal of Elementary Education	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/jee/oai
	7	Indonesian Journal of Early Childhood Education Studies	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/ijeces/oai
	8	Journal of Social and Industrial Psychology	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/sip/oai
	9	Indonesian Journal of Guidance and Counseling: Theory and Application	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/jbk/oai
	10	Journal of Non-Formal Education and Community Empowerment	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/jnfc
	11	Rainbow: Journal of Literature, Linguistics and Cultural Studies	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/rainbow/oai
	12	Journal of Lingua Litteratia	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/lel/oai
	13	Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra Indonesia	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/jpbsi/oai
	14	ELT Forum: Journal of English Language Teaching	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/elt/oai
	15	Jurnal Sastra Indonesia	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/jsi/oai

Country	Number	Journal Titles	OAI url
	16	Eduarts: Journal of Arts Education	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/eduart/oai
	17	Sutasoma: Journal of Javanese Literature	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/sutasoma/oai
	18	Piwulang Jawi: Journal of Javanese Learning and Teaching	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/piwulang/oai
	19	Chi'e: Journal of Japanese Learning and Teaching	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/chie/oai
	20	Lisanul'Arab: Journal of Arabic Learning and Teaching	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/laa/oai
	21	Jurnal Seni TariDidacticofrancia: Journal Didactique du FLE	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/jst/oai
	22	Didacticofrancia: Journal Didactique du FLE	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/dicdac/oai
	23	Jurnal Seni Musik	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/jsm/oai
	24	Arty: Journal of Visual Arts	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/arty/oai
	25	Edu Geography	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/edugeo/oai
	26	Geo-Image	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/geoimage/oai
	27	Indonesian Journal of History Education	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/ijhe/oai
	28	Journal of Indonesian History	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/jih/oai
	29	Unnes Civic Education Journal	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/ucej/oai
	30	Solidarity: Journal of Education, Society and Culture	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/solidarity/oai
	31	Unnes Law Journal	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/ulj/oai
	32	Unnes Journal of Biology Education	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/ujbe/oai
	33	Chemistry in Education	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/chemined/oai
	34	Indonesian Journal of Chemical Science	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/ijcs/oai
	35	Unnes Journal of Life Science	journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/UnnesJLifeSci/oai
	36	Unnes Journal of Mathematics	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/ujm/oai
	37	Unnes Journal of Mathematics Education	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/ujme/oai
	38	Unnes Physics Education Journal	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/upej/oai
	39	Unnes Physics Journal	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/upj/oai
	40	Unnes Science Education Journal	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/usej/oai
	41	Journal of Mechanical Engineering Learning	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/jmel/oai
	42	Automotive Science and Education Journal	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/asej/oai
	43	Scaffolding	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/scaffolding/oai
	44	Canopy: Journal of Architecture	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/Canopy/oai
	45	Edu ElektriKa Journal	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/eduel/oai
	46	Edu Komputika Journal	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/edukom/oai
	47	Food Science and Culinary Education Journal	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/fsce/oai
	48	Fashion and Fashion Education Journal	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/ffe/oai
	49	Journal of Beauty and Beauty Health Education	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/bbhe/oai
	50	Unnes Journal of Sport Sciences	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/ujss/oai
	51	ACTIVE: Journal of Physical Education, Sport, Health and Recreation	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/peshr/oai
	52	Journal of Sport Sciences and Fitness	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/jssf/oai
	53	Unnes Journal of Public Health	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/ujph/oai
	54	Accounting Analysis Journal	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/aaj/oai
	55	Economics Development Analysis Journal	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/edaj/oai
	56	Management Analysis Journal	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/maj/oai
	57	Economic Education Analysis Journal	http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/eeaj/oai
	58	UNDIP E-JOURNAL SYSTEM PORTAL	http://ejournal.undip.ac.id/index.php/index/oai
	59	Bulletin of Chemical Reaction Engineering & Catalysis	http://ejournal.undip.ac.id/index.php/bcrec/
	60	Universitas Gadjah Mada Online Journals	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/index.php/index/oai
	61	Jurnal RANAHA	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/ranah/oai
	62	Jurnal RUBIKON	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/rubikon/oai

Country	Number	Journal Titles	OAI url
	63	Jurnal Sastra Jepang	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/sastrajepang/oai
	64	Jurnal Berkala Ilmu Perpustakaan dan Informatika	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/bip/oai
	65	Jurnal Ketahanan Nasional	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jkn/oai
	66	Jurnal AL-ADAB	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/aladab/oai
	67	Jurnal POETIKA	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/poetika/oai
	68	Jurnal Sastra Perancis	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/sastraperancis/oai
	69	Jurnal ARTEFAK	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/artefak/oai
	70	Jurnal Tourisma	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/tourisma/oai
	71	Jurnal INAKOS	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/inakos/oai
	72	Lexicon	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/lexicon/oai
	73	Gajah Mada International Journal of Business	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/gamaijb/oai
	74	Majalah Geografi Indonesia	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/mgi/oai
	75	Jurnal Paradigma	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/paradigma/oai
	76	Jurnal Teknosains	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/teknosains/oai
	77	Jurnal Kawistara	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/kawistara/oai
	78	Jurnal Kajian Seni	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jks/oai
	79	Jurnal Filsafat "WISDOM"	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/wisdom/oai
	80	Indonesia Journal of Clinical Epidemiology and Biostatistics	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/ijceb/oai
	81	Journal of Information System for Public Health	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jisph/oai
	82	Acta Interna The Journal of Internal Medicine	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jain/login?source=%2Fjain
	83	Jurnal Kebijakan Kesehatan Indonesia	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jkki/oai
	84	Jurnal Pendidikan Kedokteran Indonesia	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jpki/oai
	85	Jurnal Ilmu Keperawatan	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jik/oai
	86	Journal of the Medical Sciences	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/bik/oai
	87	Berita Kedokteran Masyarakat (BKM)	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/bkm/oai
	88	Jurnal Manajemen Pelayanan Kesehatan	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jmpk/oai
	89	Jurnal Gizi Klinik Indonesia	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jgki/oai
	90	JURNAL KESEHATAN REPRODUKSI	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jkr/oai
	91	Jurnal Psikologi	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jpsi/oai
	92	Journal of Food and Pharmaceutical Sciences	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jfps/oai
	93	ASEAN Journal of Systems Engineering	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/ajse/oai
	94	Tropical Medicine Journal	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/tropmed/oai
	95	Indonesian Journal of Geography	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/ijg/oai
	96	Vegetalika	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jbp/oai
	97	Jurnal Sistem Teknik	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jst/oai
	98	Jurnal Anatomi Indonesia	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jai/oai
	99	Majalah Forum Teknik UGM	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/mft/oai
	100	Jurnal Ilmu Sosial Politik	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jurnalsospol/oai
	101	Jurnal Ilmu Kehutanan	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jikfkt/oai
	102	Jurnal Humaniora	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jurnal-humaniora/oai
	103	Jurnal Sain Veteriner	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jsv/oai
	104	Buletin Peternakan	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/buletinpeternakan/oai
	105	Jurnal Rekayasa Proses	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jrekpros/oai
	106	Jurnal Matematika, Statistika dan Aplikasinya	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jmsa/oai
	107	Jurnal Ilmu Pertanian	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jip/oai
	108	IJEIS - Indonesian Journal of Electronics and Instrumentation Systems	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/ijeis/oai
	109	IJCCS - Indonesian Journal of Computing and Cybernetics Systems	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/ijccs/oai
	110	Journal of Fisheries Sciences	http://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jfs/oai
	111	ANNALES BOGORIENSES	http://jurnal.biotek.lipi.go.id/index.php/annales/oai

Country	Number	Journal Titles	OAI url
	112	Journal of Tropical Pharmacy and Chemistry	https://jtpc.farmasi.unmul.ac.id/index.php/en/oai
	113	Jurnal Sains dan Kesehatan	https://jsk.farmasi.unmul.ac.id/index.php/id/oai
	114	Jurnal Studi Komunikasi dan Media	http://jurnal.kominfo.go.id/index.php/jskm/oai
	115	SOSIAL HORIZON: Jurnal Pendidikan Sosial	http://journal.lemlit-ikippgriptk.org/index.php/SH/oai
	116	JURNAL PENDIDIKAN INFORMATIKA DAN SAINS	http://journal.lemlit-ikippgriptk.org/index.php/Infs/oai
	117	JURNAL PENDIDIKAN OLAH RAGA	http://journal.lemlit-ikippgriptk.org/index.php/Olh/oai
	118	JURNAL PENDIDIKAN BAHASA	http://journal.lemlit-ikippgriptk.org/index.php/Bhs/oai
	119	EDUKASI: Jurnal pendidikan	http://journal.lemlit-ikippgriptk.org/index.php/Eduk/oai
	120	Jurnal INKOM	http://jurnal.informatika.lipi.go.id/index.php/inkom/oai

In this prototype, 138 journals from five countries in Southeast Asia have been managed to be harvested. User interface of SeaSciPub Index is shown in the Figure 4.

The figure displays four screenshots of the SeaSciPub Index user interface. The top-left screenshot shows the homepage with a navigation menu (HOME, ABOUT, BROWSE, SEARCH, HELP) and a user login form. The top-right screenshot shows the 'Browse' page with a list of journals including 'Journals of Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia' and 'International Journal of Integrated Engineering'. The bottom-left screenshot shows the 'Records' page for the 'Indonesian Journal of Curriculum and Educational Technology Studies', listing several articles with their titles, authors, and dates. The bottom-right screenshot shows the 'Record Details' page for a specific article, displaying a table with fields like Title, Creator, Subject, and Description.

Figure 4. User interface of SeaSciPub Index

5. CONCLUSION

According to the results of the study (Willinsky), a problem in developing public knowledge is due to the lack of access to research results. Therefore, to develop knowledge of the scientific community, a tool has to be created to access scientific papers in scientific

journals published in Southeast Asian countries. Additionally, SeaSciPub Index is also a tool for knowledge sharing among scientists in Southeast Asia.

PKP only provides information, such as the total number of OJS users from every state. They do not provide OAI url addresses. As we know, the url addresses of OAI are important to harvest the data. To obtain more complete data, it would require cooperation among journal managers in each country of Southeast Asia.

6. REFERENCES

- Czyzyk, M., & Choudhury, S. (2008, April 28). A Survey and Evaluation of Open-Source Electronic Publishing Systems. Retrieved January 2015, from <https://jscholarship.library.jhu.edu/bitstream/handle/1774.2/32737/Open%20Source%20ePublishing%20Systems%20White%20Paper.pdf?sequence=2>
- Edgar, B. D., & Willinsky, J. (n.d.). A survey of the scholarly journals using Open Journal Systems. *Scholarly and Research Communication*. <https://pkp.sfu.ca/ojs/>. (n.d.). Retrieved January 18, 2014, from <https://pkp.sfu.ca/ojs/>
- Lagoze, C., & Sompel, H. V. (n.d.). The Open Archive Initiative : Building a low-barrier interoperability framework. Retrieved January 2015, from <http://www.openarchives.org/documents/jcdl2001-oai.pdf>
- Lagoze, C., & Sompel, H. V. (n.d.). *The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting*. Retrieved January 21, 2015, from <http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/openarchivesprotocol.html>
- Lukman, Marlina, E., Sari, R. K., Akbar, A. H., & Riyanto, S. (2012). Perkembangan Open Access Jurnal Ilmiah Indonesia. *Konferensi Perpustakaan Digital Indonesia (KPDI-5) Labuan Bajo, 16-19 Oktober 2012*.
- Rajashekar, T. (n.d.). *OAI-PMH : Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting*. Retrieved January 2015, from http://www.utsc.utoronto.ca/~chan/oaindia/presentations/OAI_PMH.pdf
- Rodliyah, U. (2012, April). Perpustakaan Digital, dan Prospeknya Menuju Resource Sharing. *Visi Pustaka*, 14(1), pp. 39-47.
- Swan, A. (2012). *Policy Guidelines for the Development and Promotion of Open Access*. UNESCO.
- Willinsky, J. (n.d.). Open Journal Systems : An Example of Open Source Software for Journal Management and Publishing. Retrieved January 2015, from http://pkp.sfu.ca/files/Library_Hi_Tech_DRAFT.pdf
- www.digitaljournal.org. (n.d.).